

$$= \lfloor \frac{W_1 - f + 2p}{s} + 1 \rfloor$$

$$= \lfloor \frac{H_1 - f + 2p}{s} + 1 \rfloor$$

```

class LeNet(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, num_classes=4):
        super(LeNet, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(3, 16, 5)
        self.pool1 = nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2)
        self.conv2 = nn.Conv2d(16, 32, 5)
        self.pool2 = nn.MaxPool2d(2, 2)
        self.fc1 = nn.Linear(32*53*53, 120)
        self.fc2 = nn.Linear(120, 84)
        self.fc3 = nn.Linear(84, num_classes)

    def forward(self, x):
        x = F.relu(self.conv1(x)) # input(3, 224, 224) output(16, 220, 220)
        x = self.pool1(x) # output(16, 110, 110)
        x = F.relu(self.conv2(x)) # output(32, 104, 104)
        x = self.pool2(x) # output(32, 53, 53)
        x = x.view(-1, 32*53*53) # output(32*53*53)
        x = F.relu(self.fc1(x)) # output(120)
        x = F.relu(self.fc2(x)) # output(84)
        x = self.fc3(x) # output(4)
        return x

```

A Comparative Analysis Based on LeNet5, AlexNet, VGG16, And ResNet18 in Plankton Classification

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Abstract. Plankton is the fundamental component of the marine ecosystem and plays important roles in matter circulation and energy flow of the marine food chain. Outbreaks and invasions of plankton can also have a serious impact on the marine environment. Therefore, its observation and identification are not only fundamental to scientific research to understand marine resources, biodiversity, and the impact of climate change on the ecosystem, but also an essential tool in modern ocean management. In recent years, convolution neural network (CNN) has been actively applied in the automatic classification of plankton from their images for measurement and statistics. In this experiment, we test Plankton200, a dataset that contains 170 images and 4 categories of plankton, against AlexNet, LeNet5, VGG16, and ResNet18 respectively to test their ability to classify the images. We conclude that the training effect of ResNet18 is the best and the accuracy rate is 81.95. In addition, we perform ablation experiments on the batch size and learning rate of them. When the batch size is 8 and the learning rate is 0.01, its accuracy is the highest.

Keywords: Plankton, CNN, LeNet5, AlexNet, VGG16, ResNet18

1. Introduction

The name plankton from the Greek word *planao*, meaning to wander. They are aquatic organisms that inhabit the water column. (That is, they live away from the seabed, in the pelagic realm) and which by dint of their immobility or weak swimming capability are moved horizontally at the mercy of currents (ocean current velocities are highly variable, but are in the order of about 0.1 to 1 meter per second; millimeter-scale crustacean zooplankton swim at only tens of meters per hour)^[1].

Plankton is one of the main parts that are crucial to biologists' understanding of the Marine ecological environment. First, plankton contributes to the foundation of the marine food web. For example, phytoplankton accounts for approximately 50%^[2] of the global primary production. The food produced by phytoplankton is consumed by herbivorous zooplankton, which is crucial to a higher level of consumers such as marine mammals and sea birds. Second, many high-level consumers are planktonic during the early developing stages. *Carcinus maenas* are plankton in their juvenile form and only transform into crustaceans in adulthood. In the juvenile tense, such animals are often very fragile due to factors such as hot temperatures and predators. Third, plankton abundance and composition react sensitively to local and global environmental changes due to their selective environmental preferences. For instance, some planktons such as barber's pole worm's larvae are prone to 35 °C of water^[3]. Overall, plankton plays a vital role in the global ecology.

However, due to their diversity, manually classifying plankton is not an easy task. Automated methods to classify plankton were purposed in the 1980s. However, before 2015, all papers in that field were only using classical machine learning approaches^[4]. Afterward, deep learning approaches such as CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) were implemented. These new models are easier to set up than classical machine learning approaches and perform better at low abundances of images^[4]. However, the progress of those classifiers is difficult to track due to different dataset used by different researchers. Also, because of the diversity of the plankton, a huge open dataset that incorporates various kinds of plankton is needed to accurately classify those kinds. In addition, many current datasets now have low-quality images so they are hard for network training purposes.

We have produced a comprehensive dataset called the Plankton200 dataset. This currently incorporates 4 types of plankton with 170 images collected from the Shenzhen Bay area, but it will be update later to cover 200 different classes of plankton. Our dataset, unlike other datasets, reflects the most comprehensive information about the plankton in the Shenzhen Bay area.

The performance of the 4 basic CNN models was tested and evaluated on the Plankton200

dataset. Accuracy of those models are being compared to obtain the most suitable network. The effect of batch size and learning rate on the accuracy of the network was also examined.

The goal of this experiment is to find the network with the best performance in classifying the given classes of plankton when trained with the Plankton200 dataset.

2. Materials

The Plankton200 dataset is created to train different CNN models to classify different classes of plankton. All the images were collected from the surrounding waters of Dapeng, Shenzhen.

Compared with other plankton datasets, the Plankton200 dataset has several innovative points. First, the images in this dataset are all taken at bright field conditions. Second, the Plankton200 dataset was created with the assistance of biological experts who had made relevant reaches and experiments on plankton. Therefore, the Plankton200 dataset has certain credibility in the biology field. Last, the image samples in this dataset will continue to expand and improve the diversity of species. Samples will be collected and integrated into the Plankton200 dataset continuously. Table 1 shows the categories that are currently in the dataset and the number of images in each of them.

CATEGORY	NUMBER OF IMAGES
DIATOM	40
DINOFLAGELLATE	50
COPEPOD	40
COPEPOD LARVAE	40

Table 1. Number of images for each category in the Plankton200

2.1. Image Processing

When selecting usable samples, the samples with multiple different targets and with indistinguishable traits were rejected, and the rest were accepted. The Plankton200 dataset comprises 170 images of plankton in total, divided into four species of plankton with around 40 to 50 high-resolution images each. All images will be used as training and test samples for LeNet5, AlexNet, VGG16, and ResNet18.

To improve the recognition accuracy of the four models, all images were processed by Photoshop beforehand. The raw images are cropped with the section where the target plankton is left, then the contrast of the images is also increased for better detection. Lastly, unwanted particles and floating algae

Figure 1. The picture right left was the original image, on the right side is the picture after processed

around the plankton are also removed. Figure 1 shows a sample before and after the process.

2.2. Data Augmentation

In addition, to better fit the real-time classification scenarios, the dataset is expanded with the use of data augmentation functions such as flip, mirror, and segmentation to improve the accuracy of model training results. Doing so can not only prevent overfitting of the model and expand the dataset, but also improve the detection performance of the model.

Figure 2. Those 2 pictures show how image enhancement works, the picture on the left was the picture before enhance, the other one was the picture after enhance.

3. Methods

3.1. Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are the most popular forms of deep learning networks^[5]. They were primarily used to complete image recognition tasks through their complex architectures. Compared with networks with fully connected layers, CNN computes faster and uses less memory storage with the help of their convolutional layers by the mechanism of the feature maps. Furthermore, neural networks composed with only fully connected layers perform poorly at identifying and generalizing images. We have chosen four different classical CNN to perform our experiment. This includes LeNet5, AlexNet, VGG16, and ResNet18.

3.2. LeNet5

LeNet5^[6] is the world's first-known convolutional neural network created in 1994. As the first CNN, it comprised 7 layers in total without counting the input layers. The first convolutional layer (C1) contains 6 feature maps with a size of 28×28 and a kernel size of 5. The first down-sampling layer (S1) contains 6 feature maps with a size of 14×14 and a kernel size of 2. The second convolutional layer (C3) contains 16 feature maps with a kernel size of 5. The second subsampling layer (S4) contains 16 feature maps with a size of 5 and a kernel size of 2. The third convolutional layer (C5) contains 120 feature maps with a kernel size of 5. The last layer (F6) is a fully connected layer that is connect with C5.

Figure 3. The network architecture of LeNet5^[6]

3.3. AlexNet

AlexNet [7] is a convolutional neural network designed by Alex Krizhevsky in collaboration with Ilya Sutskever and Geoffrey Hinton. AlexNet contains eight layers with weight: the first five layers are convolutional layers while the last three layers are fully connected layers. To decrease the chance of overfitting, AlexNet introduced the idea of dropout in its network architecture. Dropout refers to the concept that neurons in the network will be randomly "ignored" or unused. This technique reduces complex co-adaptations of neurons since a neuron cannot rely on the presence of other neurons.

Figure 4. The network architecture of AlexNet [7]

3.4. VGG16

VGG16 is a convolutional neural network proposed by the Visual Geometry Group in the university of Oxford. Compared with AlexNet, VGG16 has a much deeper network. It contains 13 convolutional layer, 5 max pooling layer and 3 fully connected layer. One innovative feature of VGG16 is its decision of using several 3*3 kernel sizes instead of bigger kernel size such as 7*7 or 9*9 as proposed in the AlexNet. One benefit of using such lower kernel size is the reduction of the parameter size while having the same receptive field.[8]

Figure 5. The network architecture of VGG16

3.5. ResNet18

ResNet18 [9] is a convolutional neural network proposed by Kaiming He et al. ResNet18 contains 17 convolutional layers and 1 fully connected layer. The network is built upon Basic blocks (2 operations) and Bottleneck Block (3 operations). The problem ResNet18 trying to solve is the vanishing gradient problem. When the network became too deep, the gradient from the loss function would become zero during the backward propagation. However, by

using ResNet18, gradients can propagate back via the skip connection feature.

Figure 6. The network architecture of ResNet

4. Experiments

4.1. Experiment Setting

The comparison experiments of the four networks, variable experiments, and the data augmentation experiment are implemented on a Huawei cloud server with a NVIDIA T4 GPU. the ratio of training set size to validation set size to testing set size is set to be 8:1:1. All four networks are trained stochastic gradient descent (SGD) using back-propagation with a momentum of 0.9 and a weight decay of 0.0001. By de-fault, all images are resized to 224x224. The learning rate is set to 0.001. The number of epochs is set to 200, and the batch size is set to 32. The most accurate epoch during the training stage is adopted for the testing stage.

4.2. Network Comparison Result

After running through all the networks, the result was obtained. Among all those networks, ResNet18 has the best accuracy in both trainings (81.9%) and validation (75.0%). However, VGG16 has the best testing accuracy (85%). An explanation is that ResNet18's network depth is too deep for a dataset with around 170 images, which may lead to issues such as overfitting due to limiting sample size, thus causing a weaker generalization ability. VGG16 on the other hand has fewer layers, so the network will have a smaller probability to overfit. Future works must be done to further verify the hypothesis.

Model	Train loss	Train acc	Val loss	Val acc	Test acc (top1)
LeNet5	0.0342	61.4%	0.0514	59.8%	73%
AlexNet	0.0531	31.7%	0.0793	32.4%	39%
VGG16	0.0251	77.7%	0.0343	74.5%	85%
ResNet	0.0205	81.9%	0.0415	75.0%	79%

Table 2. The experiment result of all four networks

Among all the following networks, it can be seen from table 2 that AlexNet has the weakest

performance in all three stages (31.7%, 32.4%, and 39%). The explanation for that is that AlexNet has no optimization operation that can solve the gradient vanishing problem unlike VGG16 or ResNet18 [7]. Since the size of the dataset is small for a deep network, AlexNet cannot learn enough features from the images, thus making it incapable of classifying planktons.

4.3. Batch Size And Learning Rate Experiment

We then test the effect of batch size on the maximum validation accuracy of ResNet18 since it has the best performance during training and validation. With all other variables being constant, the batch size is set to be 8, 64, and 128 each time. Fig. 7 shows that when the batch size is 8, it has the greatest maximum validation accuracy. For larger batch sizes like 64 and 128, even though they result in a less frequent fluctuation, they have a lower maximum validation accuracy. Masters and Luschi [10] had empirically proved that using small batch sizes that are less than or equal to 32 can obtain the best training stability and generalization ability with a given amount of computation time. For batch sizes larger than 32, they have a larger possibility to stuck in the saddle points during stochastic gradient descend. On the other head, smaller batch sizes can result in jump out of the local minima^[11]. The number of epochs was not considered in comparing the effect of different batch sizes, which will be done as a part of the future work.

The relationship between the learning rate on the maximum validation accuracy was then tested. With all other variables being constant, we set the learning rate to 0.1, 0.001, and 0.0001 each time. From Fig. 8, it can be shown that 0.001 has the best maximum validation accuracy (94%). This shows that the learning rate cannot be set too high or too low; it must be in somewhere between. The reason is that when the learning rate is too big, it can easily pass the optimal point in the loss function, when the learning rate is too low, it will take a huge amount of time for the accuracy graph to converge.

Figure 7. The validation accuracy graph with the three different batch size (8, 64, 128 respectively)

Figure 8. The validation accuracy graph with the three different learning rates (0.1, 0.001, 0.0001 respectively)

4.4. Confusion Matrix

From Fig. 9, it can be shown from the confusion matrix of all four networks that all four networks have a low score when classifying Copepods and their larvae. The reason giving that Copepods' larvae look like the adult such that there are few distinguishable traits, as a result, the network struggles to differentiate. Also, due to the limited size of the dataset, it is hard for the networks to learn the differentiable traits between the two categories.

4.5. Data argumentation

Lastly, we examine the effect of data argumentation on the generalization ability of ResNet18. We randomly assign two operations out of rotation, vertical flip, horizontal flip, scaling up, and perspective change. Fig.10 shows one of the processed images. After the data argumentation, the size of the dataset doubled, and the testing accuracy went from 76% to 89%.

5. Discussion

The development of the CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) could be summed up in the following order: the problem of underfitting approaches to enhance the model's ability to generalize, deeper neural networks, overfitting, and gradient vanishing problems, the development of skip connections, and further innovative ways to improve the model's performance.

As shown in the experiments, deeper neural networks do not necessarily grantee better accuracy. In the case of AlexNet, the network did not obtain a result better than LeNet5 due the nature of its feature. When a deep network encounters a small dataset with a size such as 170 in this case, it will have the issue of overfitting when it does not have any features that solve the problem. Also, for the case of ResNet18, it did not have the expected inference performance due to its deep layer. In this case, because the small size of the dataset, ResNet18 will run in the problem of overfitting since there are few samples for it to learn.

As one aspect of ways in improving the model's ability to generalize, data argumentation is

extremely effective in solving the problem brought by smaller-scale datasets. It allows the model to generalize images from different angles and lighting, which would be beneficial in improving its training and test accuracy. As another aspect of ways in influencing the model's performance, batch size and learning rate also becomes important. Models would perform better with smaller batch sizes due to the problem of the generalization gap brought by bigger batch sizes in training. However, it is proven that the problem of the generalization gap is not inherently unsolvable, and large batch sizes could generalize as well as models trained by small batches.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we explored the Plankton200 dataset through the following steps: dataset building and optimization, classification, data augmentation, and result interpretation. From our experiment, we could conclude that VGG16 network performed the best in terms of generalization and validation accuracy (top 1) with default parameters (0.001 learning rate, 200 epochs, 32 batch size). All models were trained on a Tesla T4 GPU. Notably, ResNet18 had the best training and validation accuracy with the default parameters probably because of its residual networks.

Figure 9. The confusion matrix of LeNet5, AlexNet, VGG16, ResNet18 respectively

Figure 10. The comparison between an original image and its replica with two random image operation

To improve the model's ability to generalize upon various angles and lighting of the raw images for the different classes of Plankton, data augmentation techniques was also used through our experiments. By adding images that is further transformed (rotation, flip, scaling) to the training set, the validation accuracy(top1) was improved from 76% to 89%.

Furthermore, through our experiments with the ResNet18 alone, we found out that smaller batch size leads to higher rate of fluctuations in validation accuracy graph during the 200 epochs, but the validation accuracy reached the highest point at 94% which comparatively performs much better than 64 and 128 batch size. With learning rate experiment, we tested through our experiment with ResNet18 and it appeared that with learning rate of 0.001, model performed the best in terms of generalization.

It is apparent that 170 images for the dataset is not enough for the model's ability to generalize. Therefore, further work of this paper would be primarily focus on the augmentation of dataset size and to achieve not only classification of different classes of plankton but also detection as well.

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